

POLYNUCLEAR AROMATIC HYDROCARBONS. PART III. A NEW ROUTE TO CHRYSENE DERIVATIVES

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A convenient route to chrysene derivatives has been developed on the basis of cationoid reaction between aromatic substances and $\gamma\delta$ -unsaturated ketones, and the synthesis of 2-methyl- and 2:5-dimethylchrysene by this route is described.

In earlier communications (Mukherji *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, 17, 1202; 1953, 18, 1499; 1954, 19, 328; *Nature*, 1951, 168, 1003; *Science & Culture*, 1952, 18, 152) it was shown how aluminium chloride-catalysed cationoid reaction between aromatic substances and $\gamma\delta$ -unsaturated ketones, esters and amides could be wielded to furnish convenient routes to naphthalene, phenanthrene, 3:4-benzphenanthrene, polyphenyl and isoquinoline systems. Recently, we also reported (this *Journal*, 1955, 32, 697) a successful extension of this method to the synthesis of anthracene and 1:2-benzanthracene derivatives. Phillips and McWhorter (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 4948) have applied our method to the synthesis of methylchrysene and Diel's hydrocarbon by variation of the aromatic component. We now describe the experiments undertaken to extend the scope of this method to the synthesis of chrysene systems, by varying the ketonic component in the cationoid reaction.

The starting material, β -tetralone, was best prepared by following the conditions of Birch (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 430) for reduction of β -naphthol. Monoallylation of β -tetralone was smoothly effected in 61% yield by its reaction with sodamide, followed by allyl iodide. But the ketone (I) failed to provide any solid 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone or semicarbazone, although it analysed well for the required composition. It rapidly developed coloration on exposure to air and sunlight.

The Friedel-Crafts alkylation of benzene with 1-allyl-2-tetralone under the conditions laid down by Mukherji and Bhattacharyya (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, 17, 1202) furnished 1-(β -methyl- β -phenylethyl)-2-tetralone (IIa) in 56% yield. This ketone was reduced (Ponndorf) in an excellent yield to the corresponding alcohol (IIIa) which was cyclised with concentrated sulphuric acid to obtain a product, which may be represented as (IVa) and/or (Va), the corresponding spiran.

The possible formation of a spiran, such as (Va), could be rationalised by a consideration of the low nucleophilicity of the aromatic system which allows the reaction to proceed in a non-concerted manner (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, *77*, 5068) with the intermediate formation of the better initiating carbonium ion (VIIa), because on energetic grounds the carbonium ion (VIIa) will be more stable than (VIIIa). Again, a non-concerted acid-catalysed cyclisation to a six-membered ring, such as in (IV), would result in a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*-isomers. However, the objective of the present work being the synthesis of fully aromatised structures, the above points, *i.e.*, the relative proportions of the six-membered cyclised product (IVa) and the spiran (Va), and of the relative proportions of the *cis*- and *trans*- isomers of (IVa) were not studied at present.

The product of cyclisation, on dehydrogenation with 30% palladium-charcoal, furnished a pale resinous mass which did not solidify on standing in the cold but afforded a dark red picrate, which on repeated crystallisations corresponded with the picrate of 2-methylchrysenes. Regeneration of the pure hydrocarbon (VIa) was effected by treating the purified picrate with dilute aqueous ammonia, and the melting point of the regenerated hydrocarbon corresponded very well with that of 2-methylchrysenes.

Literature records many examples of acid-catalysed cyclisation where varying amounts of spirans have been reported (*J. Chem. Soc.* 1933, 1098 ; *J. Org. Chem.*, 1936, 1, 288). But Harper *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 124) demonstrated that the spiran formation was very much diminished or even completely avoided by the introduction of a methyl group in the 2-position of the unsaturated intermediate, such as

This improved method for cyclisation to six-membered ring was later utilised among others by Cook *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1934, 653, 1727).

In order to suppress or avoid the possible formation of the spiran (Va) in the cyclisation of (III), the ketone (IIa) was allowed to react upon with excess of methylmagnesium iodide and the resulting carbinol (IXa), obtained in 81% yield, was cyclised with concentrated sulphuric acid. The cyclised product (Xa) was then dehydrogenated with 30% palladium-charcoal to furnish the hydrocarbon (VIa), the angular methyl group having been knocked off during the process. The over-all yield of the hydrocarbon (VIa) by this process was found to be better than when the ketone (IIa) was directly reduced, cyclised and aromatised. It appears therefore that the presence of the spiran (Va) adversely affects the aromatisation step.

2-Methylchrysene was earlier synthesised by Fieser *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 2134), Newman (*ibid.*, 1938, 60, 2947), Bradsher (*ibid.*, 1940, 62, 3190) and Marvel *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1940, 62, 2659). The physical properties of our product and that of its picrate agree very well with those recorded by these American workers.

We then proceeded to synthesise by a similar procedure the hitherto-unknown compound, 2:5-dimethylchrysene. Under the influence of anhydrous aluminium chloride, toluene condensed with 1-allyl-2-tetralone (I) to furnish 1-[β -methyl- β -(*p*-tolyl)-ethyl]-2-tetralone (IIb) in 62% yield. The *para*-orientation in this product (cf. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, 19, 328; this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 1) was established by its oxidation with alkaline potassium permanganate, when a mixture of phthalic and terephthalic acids was obtained. The latter was separated by fractional crystallisation and identified through its dimethyl ester. No trace of *isophthalic* acid could be detected.

In the light of our experience in the synthesis of 2-methylchrysene, the ketone (IIb) was allowed to react with methylmagnesium iodide, and the resulting carbinol (IXb), obtained in 76% yield, was cyclised with H_2SO_4 (conc.) in the usual way to furnish (Xb) in 60% yield. This hexahydro derivative was then aromatised with palladium-charcoal catalyst (30%) to obtain a viscous mass in 70% yield, which readily furnished a deep orange picrate. The pure hydrocarbon, 2:5-dimethylchrysene (VIb), was regenerated from its picrate.

* EXPERIMENTAL

1-Allyl-2-tetralone (I).—To a cooled suspension of sodamide (prepared from 2.5 g. of sodium in anhydrous ammonia with a small crystal of ferric nitrate as catalyst) in anhydrous ether (100 c.c.) was added dropwise a solution of β -tetralone (14.6 g.) in anhydrous ether (75 c.c.) with stirring. The mixture, after standing for 2 hours to attain room temperature, was refluxed on the steam-bath for 6 hours. The contents were then cooled in the ice-bath and allyl iodide (16 g.) in benzene (50 c.c.) was added gradually, and the mixture was let stand at room temperature for one hour. It was then refluxed on the steam-bath for 6 hours and decomposed with iced HCl. The aqueous layer was repeatedly extracted with ether and the combined ether-benzene layer was washed free of acid, dried (Na_2SO_4) and the solvent removed. The residue on distillation under reduced pressure furnished 11.4 g. (61%) of 1-allyl-2-tetralone as a pale yellow liquid, b.p. $140^\circ\text{--}145^\circ/5$ mm. (Found: C, 84.12; H, 7.48. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$ requires C, 83.83; H, 7.58 per cent).

1-(β -Methyl- β -phenylethyl)-2-tetralone (IIa).—To a solution of 1-allyl-2-tetralone (9.3 g., 0.05 M) in benzene (100 c.c.), kept below 5° , was added anhydrous aluminium chloride (13.4 g., 0.1 M) gradually with stirring during a period of 40 minutes. After the addition was complete, stirring was continued for 4 hours and the temperature was allowed to rise up to 20° during the last hour. The deep brown reaction mixture was then poured on iced HCl. The organic layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted with ether. The combined extract was washed free of acid and then dried (Na_2SO_4). On removal of the solvent, the residue furnished on distillation 7.4 g. (56%) of 1-(β -methyl- β -phenylethyl)-2-tetralone as a mobile liquid, b.p. $240^\circ\text{--}245^\circ/6$ mm. (Found: C, 86.10; H, 7.62. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}$ requires C, 86.32; H, 7.63 per cent).

1-(β -Methyl- β -phenylethyl)-2-tetralol (IIIa).—The above ketone (5.3 g.) was subjected to the Ponndorf reduction with aluminium isopropoxide, prepared from 2.5 g. of aluminium foil and 75 c.c. of isopropyl alcohol. The reduced product was worked up in the usual manner to obtain 3.84 g. (72%) of (IIIa) as a viscous mass, b.p. $225^\circ\text{--}230^\circ/4$ mm. (Found: C, 86.17; H, 7.88. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}$ requires C, 85.67; H, 8.33 per cent).

Cyclisation of (IIIa).—The tetralol (IIIa: 7 g.) was treated with H_2SO_4 (conc., 7 c.c.) at $0^\circ\text{--}5^\circ$ for 4 hours. After working up in the usual way, the product yielded on distillation 3.14 g. (48%) of a very viscous glassy mass, distilling at $215^\circ\text{--}222^\circ/6$ mm. (Found: C, 91.54; H, 8.00. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{20}$ requires C, 91.88; H, 8.12 per cent).

2-Methylchryse (VIa).—The above cyclised product (3 g.) was dehydrogenated by heating it with 30% Pd—C catalyst (0.3 g.) at 300° when there was a brisk evolution of hydrogen. Heating was continued for 5 hours, temperature being raised to 330° during the later stage. The product was worked up in the usual manner and distilled under reduced pressure to obtain 1.6 g. of a resinous mass distilling at $215^\circ\text{--}220^\circ/4$ mm., which did not solidify. This mass was then converted into its picrate (1.1 g.) which melted at $169\text{--}70^\circ$ on twice crystallisation from petroleum ether (b.p. $60^\circ\text{--}80^\circ$). [Newman (*loc. cit.*), m.p. $170\text{--}173.6^\circ$; Fieser (*loc. cit.*), m.p. $169.8\text{--}170.2^\circ$; Marvel, (*loc. cit.*), m.p. $171\text{--}72^\circ$]. (Found: N, 8.95. Calc. for $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_7\text{N}_3$: N, 8.91 per cent).

* Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Analyses by Drs. Weiler and Strauss, Oxford.

The above picrate (1 g.) was treated with a dilute aqueous solution of ammonia, when a light coloured solid separated out (120 mg.) which on twice crystallisation from petroleum ether (b.p. 60°-80°) furnished pure 2-methylchrysene, m.p. 160° Lit. m.p. 161-161.4° (Newman, *loc. cit.*); m.p. 159-159.8° (Fieser, *loc. cit.*); m.p. 160-161.4° (Marvel, *loc. cit.*). (Found: C, 93.86; H, 5.75. Calc. for C₁₈H₁₄: C, 94.18; H, 5.82 per cent).

1-(β-Methyl-β-phenylethyl)-2-methyl-2-tetralol (IXa).—To a solution of methylmagnesium iodide, prepared from methyl iodide (4.3 g.), magnesium turnings (0.72 g.) and dry ether (20 c.c.), was added gradually and with cooling the ketone (IIa: 5.3 g.) in 10 c.c. of dry ether. After standing for 2 hours, the reaction mixture was refluxed on the steam-bath for 4 hours and then decomposed with cold dilute HCl. The hydrolysate on being worked up in the usual way furnished 4.54 g. (81%) of (IXa), b.p. 190-92°/4 mm. (Found: C, 85.88; H, 8.20. C₂₀H₂₄O requires C, 85.66; H, 8.63 per cent).

2:15-Dimethyl-1:2:7:8:15:16-hexahydrochrysene (Xa).—The above tetralol (IXa: 3 g.) was cyclised with H₂SO₄ (conc., 3 c.c.) at 0° for 4 hours. On working up in the usual way, 1.68 g. (60%) of the hexahydro derivative (Xa) was obtained, b.p. 178-80°/6 mm. (Found: C, 91.25; H, 8.45. C₂₀H₂₂ requires C, 91.55; H, 8.45 per cent).

Dehydrogenation of (Xa).—The hexahydro derivative (Xa: 1.5 g.) was dehydrogenated with 30% Pd—C catalyst (0.15 g.) at 300°-330° for 4 hours. The product on working up in the usual manner furnished 1 g. of a colorless viscous mass, distilling at 210°-215°/3 mm., which produced an orange picrate (1.1 g.), m.p. 169° (crystallised from alcohol), undepressed on admixture with the picrate prepared previously. The pure hydrocarbon (VIa) was regenerated from this picrate in the usual manner, and on crystallisation from petroleum ether it melted at 160°, undepressed by admixture with the earlier sample.

1-[β-Methyl-β-(p-tolyl)-ethyl]-2-tetralone (IIb).—1-Allyl-2-tetralone (I: 9.3 g.) was allowed to react with pure toluene (100 c.c.) in presence of AlCl₃ (anhyd., 13.4 g.) under the conditions laid down for (IIa) to obtain 8.6 g. (62%) of the tetralone (IIb), b.p. 252-55°/4 mm. (Found: C, 86.64; H, 7.77. C₂₀H₂₂O requires C, 86.28; H, 7.97 per cent).

Oxidation of the Tetralone (IIb).—The tetralone (IIb: 1 g.) was oxidised by refluxing it with a 5% KMnO₄ solution. The product on acidification yielded a mixture of phthalic and terephthalic acids. The latter was separated by taking advantage of its very low solubility in water and was then converted into dimethyl ester, m.p. 141° (undepressed when mixed with an authentic sample).

1-[β-Methyl-β-(p-tolyl)-ethyl]-2-methyl-2-tetralol (IXb).—The ketone (IIb: 5.56 g.) was treated with methylmagnesium iodide, prepared from methyl iodide (4.4 g.), magnesium turnings (0.72 g.) and anhydrous ether (20 c.c.). After keeping the mixture for 2 hours, followed by refluxing on the steam-bath for 4 hours, the complex was decomposed with cold dilute HCl. On usual working up, 4.47 g. (76%) of the tetralol (IIb) was obtained, b.p. 258-60°/4 mm. (Found: C, 85.43; H, 8.63. C₂₂H₂₆O requires C, 85.66; H, 8.90 per cent).

2:5:15-Trimethyl-1:2:7:8:15:16-hexahydrochrysene (Xb).—The cyclisation of the above tetralol (4 g.) was effected by its treatment with H_2SO_4 (conc., 4 c.c.) at $0^\circ-5^\circ$ for 4 hours, when, on working up in the usual way, 2.25 g. (60%) of the hexahydro derivative (Xb) was obtained, b.p. $242-45^\circ/5$ mm. (Found: C, 90.80; H, 8.34. $C_{21}H_{24}$ requires C, 91.25; H, 8.75 per cent).

2:5-Dimethylchrysene (VIb).—The hexahydro derivative (Xb; 2 g.) was dehydrogenated by heating it with 0.2 g. of 30% Pd—C catalyst at $300^\circ-330^\circ$ for 4 hours. On working up, the product furnished 1.3 g. of a viscous mass, b.p. $250^\circ-255^\circ/4$ mm., which readily gave a deep orange picrate, crystallised from alcohol, m.p. $156-57^\circ$. (Found: N, 8.30. $C_{26}H_{18}O_7N_3$ requires N, 8.66 per cent).

The parent hydrocarbon, 2:5-dimethylchrysene, was regenerated from the picrate by means of dilute aqueous ammonia. After crystallisation from petroleum ether (b.p. $60^\circ-80^\circ$) 2:5-dimethylchrysene (1.04 g.) melted at $150-51^\circ$. (Found: C, 93.30; H, 6.00. $C_{26}H_{18}$ requires C, 93.71; H, 6.29 per cent).

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